

JOURNAL OF ENGLISH STUDIES

ISSN : 3122-0479

DOI – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18037035>

Volume 1 No 1 December (2025): Journal of English Studies

MULTIMODAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF SELECTED FLYERS ON CHILDREN-RELATED DISEASES IN NIGERIA

<https://joesfudutsinma.com.ng/joes/index.php/one/article/view/18>

joesfudma@gmail.com

Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola

Department of English and Literary Studies

Faculty of Arts

Federal University Lokoja

popoolapeace22@gmail.com

+2348100418083

Peter Ochefu Okpeh, PhD

Department of English and Literary Studies

Faculty of Arts

Federal University Lokoja

peter.okpeh@fulokoja.edu

+2348068242965

ABSTRACT

This study focused on the multimodal discourse analysis of selected public health flyers on children-related diseases in Nigeria. It investigated how various semiotic modes are utilised and integrated to communicate health information effectively. While previous studies on health communication in Nigeria have focused primarily on textual analysis or verbal discourse, there remains a significant gap in the exploration of how multimodal strategies function in public health messaging, particularly concerning child-related diseases. This research filled that gap by providing an in-depth analysis of 5 purposively selected flyers targeting five major diseases affecting children: malaria, pneumonia, HIV/AIDS, diarrhoea, and measles. This study is grounded in Holaran's framework of Multimodal Discourse Analysis, which focuses on how different modes are integrated to enhance. Different modes in each of the flyers were identified and analysed. Findings revealed that the selected flyers strategically integrate multiple modes to enhance message clarity, emotional appeal, and audience engagement. The study concluded that multimodal discourse is a powerful and necessary approach in the design of effective health communication materials.

Key Words: public health flyers, children-related diseases.

Introduction

Child-related diseases refer to medical conditions and infections that primarily affect children, especially under the age of five, often resulting from factors such as malnutrition, poor sanitation, lack of vaccination, and weak health systems. These include diseases like malaria, measles, pneumonia, diarrhoea, and pediatric HIV/AIDS (Black et al., 2010; WHO, 2023; UNICEF, 2021). According to (UNCF, 2001), the major infectious diseases of children in Nigeria and other parts of Africa are malaria, diarrhoea, respiratory diseases, particularly pneumonia, and Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS). Others include chickenpox, diphtheria, influenza, measles, meningitis, polio, and whooping cough, among others. Most of these diseases are preventable (for example, malaria, pneumonia, diarrhoea, and Human Immunodeficiency); unfortunately, they are still killing children in large numbers. Pneumonia, diarrhoea and malaria were responsible for approximately 29 per cent of global deaths among children under the age of 5 in 2018, according to the WHO (2020). Also, data from the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2013) indicates that under-five mortality rates are higher in Northern Nigeria than in Southern Nigeria. According to the data, The North-West records the highest rate of 185 deaths per 1000 live births, followed by the North-East and the North-Central with 160 deaths and 100 deaths per 1000 live births in that order, while the South-East, South-South and South-West record 131, 091 and 90 deaths per 1000 live births respectively (NPC and ICF International, 2014). The report further shows that socioeconomic, environmental and cultural factors influence mortality rates.

The foregoing reveals that childhood diseases pose a significant health risk in Nigeria, making the issue of health communication crucial in disease prevention and management. In line with this, the Nigerian government has implemented several initiatives to address some of these diseases and to improve child health outcomes; in response to Nigeria's High malaria burden, the government has introduced the Oxford R21 vaccine, which has shown 75 per cent effectiveness

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
in preventing severe malaria in children. Another initiative is the National Health Initiative established by the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA). The use of language to effectively communicate relevant information, as well as create awareness on how to prevent and cure these diseases, is key because improper use of language can result in the message being misunderstood, misinterpreted, misheard, ignored, or perceived as irrelevant. The effectiveness of health communication thus helps to promote public health. This informs the need for effective health communication and proper enlightenment of the public to address these serious issues that affect children and young adults, and sometimes even lead to their death.

Health communication is a vital component of health promotion, enabling individuals, groups, and communities to make informed decisions about their health. It involves the use of various communication strategies, channels, and techniques to inform, educate, and persuade people to adopt healthy behaviour and make informed health decisions. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2013), health communication is "the process of planning, executing, and evaluating messages and programmes to promote health, prevent disease, and enhance quality of life". Effective health communication takes into account the social, cultural, and environmental context of the target audience, as emphasised by Kreps 1988).

Health education creates awareness and influences behaviours in people by equipping the public with tools and knowledge that enable them to respond appropriately to health crises and various health challenges. In most cases, health education is carried out through the use of flyers and posters, where awareness is created to address a particular disease and pass vital information to the public. This informs decision-making that will influence a healthy lifestyle by taking necessary measures to prevent disease, maintain and improve their health. Health flyers are therefore widely used in Nigeria to disseminate health information. However, the effectiveness of these flyers depends on several factors, including clear messaging, visual appeal, and the relevance of their content to the audience, among others. Based on the foregoing, this study aims to explore the multimodal discourse analysis of selected flyers on children-related diseases in

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)** Nigeria. To achieve this, the different modes used in communication, the integration of these modes, and the semiotic resources used to enhance the clarity of the intended message will be discussed.

Previous Studies on the Use of Language in Medical Settings

Odebunmi (2006) critically examines the pragmatic roles that locutionary acts play in understanding the communication between doctors and patients in Southwestern Nigeria. John Austin's locutionary acts are used for analysis, with restrictions to the lexical occurrences and lexical relationships observed in the discourse. The findings reveal that two categories of locutions were engaged in hospital interactions, namely, locutions intended to be understood by non-professionals and locutions not intended to be understood by non-professionals. The paper observes that locutions in medical discourse in Southwestern Nigeria bring standard lexical choices and local linguistic initiatives of medical practitioners into a pragmatic union. It therefore concludes that the pragmatic engagement of these choices displays the tact the practitioners use in dealing with patients. This work is relevant to the current research in terms of its similarity in the type of discourse. They are both in medical discourse. It is different in theory and data.

Oyebode and Unuabona (2013) critically analysed selected HIV/AIDS. A study was conducted by Franz and Murphy (2018) on Reconsidering the role of language in medicine. In the study, the authors considered how different models of language use, which have been proposed in the philosophical literature, might be applied to communication in medicine. In particular, the authors contrasted the traditional, indexical thesis of language with new models that focus on interpretation instead of standardisation. The authors demonstrated how paying close attention to the role of language in medicine provides a philosophical foundation for supporting recent changes in doctor-patient communication. The findings of the study further revealed that interpretive models of language use provide an important rationale for facilitating a more robust dialogue between doctors and patients. This work is relevant to the current work in terms of its

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
similarity in the type of discourse. They both focus on medical discourse. They differ in theory and data.

Olajimbite (2025) critically examined Deontic Modality and Evaluation of Obligations in Children-related X (Twitter) Interactions. This study examines the strategic use of deontic modality in evaluating obligations in children-related X (Twitter) interactions. Data for the study were part of a larger project corpus of 285,015 tweets with 2,819,696 tokens collected between July 2023 and July 2024 using the Apify Twitter Scraper. The study adopted a mix of corpus-based methodologies and qualitative discourse analysis (QDA) as data were coded and sorted using Laurence Anthony's AntConc. For the corpus-based method, a keyness analysis, which highlighted deontic modality elements, should and must, as keywords and KIWC were done as well as the manual sorting of the data. Martin and White (The language of evaluation: Appraisal in English, Palgrave Macmillan, 2005). The Appraisal framework foregrounds the QDA. Findings reveal implicit and explicit evaluative constructions manifesting individual, parental, institutional, and societal obligations in domains bordering on trafficking, assault, killing, education, health, and indoctrination. These deontic obligations were constructed through inscribed and evoked strategies as online participants evaluate social sanction of capacity and morality, social esteem of veracity, and appreciation of valuation; thereby strongly condemning, and calling for actions and accountability from individuals, groups, and institutions within the social context of leadership on children's well-being. This study is relevant to the current study in terms of its similarity in the type of discourse. They both focus on paediatric discourse. They differ in data and theory.

Methodology

Data for this study includes five (50) health flyers on child health-related issues prevalent in Nigeria that were selected for analysis. The flyers are grouped into five categories based on the five major diseases peculiar to children and young adults. These are malaria, pneumonia, diarrhoea, measles and HIV. In each group, 4 flyers will be analysed in the sample analysis. The

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
study adopts a qualitative content analysis method guided by O' Hollaran's (2004) framework on Multimodal Discourse Analysis. Each flyer is analysed by identifying and interpreting the use of different modes: Linguistic mode: sentence structure, word choice, and text type. Visual mode: images, colour, layout, typography, size. Gestural mode: posture, facial expression, and body movement in images. Spatial mode: layout, placement of elements, reading path. Semiotic resources: intensity, foregrounding, backgrounding, framing, and salience. This mode-based analysis helps to reveal how the integration of 3 semiotic resources enhance the flyer's effectiveness in communicating health messages.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in O'Holloran's (2004) framework of Multimodal Discourse Analysis. It considers all communicative elements in a text or visual medium. It looks at different modes of communication and how they work together. These modes include: Linguistic Mode, Visual Mode, Spatial Mode, Gestural Mode and Aural Mode. Each of these modes contributes to meaning-making and affects how the audience interprets the message in a text. Textual Analysis (Linguistic Mode) examines the choice of words, sentence structure, and persuasive techniques. It identifies whether the language is formal or informal, scientific or simple and also determines whether the writer uses commands or persuasive appeals. Image Analysis (Visual Mode) involves analysing the types of images used, the application of colour psychology, and the symbolism present in the images, as well as the meaning conveyed by the symbols used. The Spatial Mode (Layout and Composition) deals with how text and images are arranged (that is, the elements are most prominent). Hierarchy is an aspect of spatial mode that deals with the font size of words in a text. Hierarchy also deals with the readability and accessibility of words in a text. Gestural mode deals with the facial expression and body language of the human figures in the images in the text, and how these gestures contribute to meaning making. Semiotic analyses examine cultural symbols and their contributions to meaning-making. In contrast, the aural mode focuses on digital media, including the use of voice-overs or music, for meaning-making.

In the theory, O'Halloran argues that these resources function together in an integrated system, rather than existing independently. For instance, in a flyer about children-related diseases, the combination of textual information (e.g., symptoms, prevention tips), visual elements (e.g., images of sick children, doctors, or medical equipment), and color schemes (e.g., red for urgency, blue for trust) work together to influence how readers interpret the message. Applying this framework of MDA to the current study, MDA examines the choice of words, sentence structures and persuasive techniques used in the flyers on children-related diseases. Through this framework, the analyst determines whether the flyers use commands or persuasive appeals; all these can be analysed under the textual analysis. The visual mode deals with how texts and images are arranged. Colour symbolism, font sizes, facial expressions and so on are also analysed. This theoretical model of MDA is relevant to the current work because it enables a comprehensive analysis of the different modes used in communication by integrating the tenets of text, visuals and context. The theory also helps in understanding how meaning is constructed in health communication.

In applying the theory to the current research, attention will be focused on such tenets of the theory as linguistic analysis, visual analysis, spatial analysis, as well as semiotic analysis. These aspects of this framework are selected because they help to achieve the stated aim and objectives of the study. The aural mode will not be used because it deals with digital media.

Analysis and Findings

This section focuses on the presentation, description, and analysis of the data collected for the study. Specifically, it examines twenty selected public health flyers addressing diseases related to children in Nigeria. The aim is to uncover how different semiotic modes linguistic, visual, spatial, and gestural interact to construct meaning, persuade, and inform target audiences. Five (5) health flyers on child health-related issues prevalent in Nigeria are selected for analysis. The flyers are grouped into five based on the five major diseases peculiar to children and young adults.

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
These are malaria, pneumonia, diarrhoea, measles and HIV. In each group, 1 flyer will be analysed.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

MALARIA DISEASE

TEXT 1

Text 1: We can Stop Malaria

The above text has a combination of two modes: the linguistic mode and the visual mode. What follows is an analysis of each of these modes, the semiotic resources deployed in them, and how the modes interact to pass the intended message to the audience.

Linguistic Mode Analysis

Within the linguistic mode, features such as sentence types, lexical choices and syntactic properties are used in the text to construct meaning. These are further enhanced through rhetorical

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
strategies such as foregrounding, Intensity and backgrounding, which draw attention to key messages and amplify their communicative impact.

In text 1 above, the sentence " We Can STOP MALARIA" is a declarative sentence that affirms the possibility of ending the spread of the malaria disease. Generally, declarative sentences are short and simple and are used to express facts or information. They are straightforward and easy to understand, as noted by Reddish (2001). In the text under analysis, the sentence is used to achieve clarity, readability and conciseness. The use of the declarative here helps the audience to quickly understand the information passed about the possibility of preventing the malaria disease. To ensure immediate recognition and emphasis, the predicate component of the declarative,, " STOP MALARIA", is stylistically foregrounded. Foregrounding in linguistic analysis is a stylistic strategy used to draw the attention of readers to a particular element in a message, making it stand out from the rest, in order to catch the viewer's eye or thought. This is achieved through the use of capital letters, repetition, rhetorical questions, among others, as noted by Kress and Leeuwen (2006). In the text above, foregrounded elements, "STOP MALARIA" are deliberately intended to disrupt the normal flow of the text, grabbing the attention of the audience to the urgency of the message. It is also a call to action in preventing malaria disease.

The supporting text " Sleep under a mosquito net every night" is another declarative sentence used in the text to achieve clarity and readability. Beyond its clarity, this sentence is also deliberately backgrounded. Backgrounded are elements placed behind foregrounded elements to provide context for the main message without distracting the reader from the main message as noted by Kress and Leeuwen 2006. In the text, the background linguistic elements " Sleep under mosquito net every night" subtly reinforce the message. It does not distract the reader from the main message, yet it emphasises the preventive measure by giving a practical directive.

Under the lexical choice," We "in "We Can STOP MALARIA" is an inclusive pronoun. Inclusive pronouns are personal pronouns that put the writer and reader in the same group. This is to achieve unity, shared responsibility and collective identity between the campaigners and the audience.

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
van Dijk (1998:43) notes that " inclusive pronouns are used to build solidarity and create a sense of collectivity. In the text, the use of the inclusive pronoun "we " is to engage the reader directly. Also included in the lexical aspect of the linguistic analysis is the use of the modal verb "can" in the text. Modal verbs are auxiliary verbs that express a speaker's attitude or mood towards the action or state described by the main verb. They show possibility, ability or obligation. In the text above, the modal verb" in "We Can STOP MALARIA" is used to show the possibility of the prevention of the disease.

Visual Mode Analysis

Within the visual mode, images and colours are used to communicate. This is done through the use of semiotic resources like intensity, framing and foregrounding, among others. These resources are used to enhance communication and to amplify the meaning of the message. The visual resources employed in the text above are the use of images, colours and fonts. The message communicated through these resources is further reinforced by the rhetorical device of intensity, which is meant to amplify the message and guide interpretations.

In the text above, the image of a mosquito placed in a prohibition symbol is used to suggest the danger of mosquitoes. It is a call to prompt action in taking preventive measures against it. It intensifies the message passed by the linguistic elements " we can stop malaria" and also shows that mosquitoes are a transmitter of malaria disease and must be prevented to avoid the disease. The central image of the mosquito is used because it is universally recognised as a vector for malaria.

The message is further intensified by the font size of the mosquito, which. Is exaggerated to draw the attention of the audience to the danger in it. The red colour is also used to reinforce the message of danger in mosquitoes' bites visually. Red colour generally connotes danger and alarm, as noted by Kress and Leeuwen (2002). It is used in the flyer for the image of the prohibition symbol to indicate danger, seriousness and to raise alarm.

Integration of Modes

The two modes (linguistic and visual) are integrated to make the message of malaria prevention more precise, succinct and pungent. The image reinforces the text; the crossed-out mosquito connects directly to stopping malaria. The text explains the image; without it, a viewer might interpret the message as general mosquito awareness. The words give it context and purpose. Together, they form a complete communication unit: the visual grabs the attention and the text delivers the message. With this, communication is enhanced because viewers instantly understand the flyer's intent without confusion.

PNEUMONIA DISEASE

TEXT 2: World Pneumonia Day

The above text has a combination of two modes: the linguistic mode and the visual mode. What follows is an analysis of each of these modes, the semiotic resources deployed in them, and how the modes interact to pass the intended message to the audience.

Linguistic Mode Analysis

Within the linguistic mode, features such as sentence types, lexical choices and syntactic properties are used in the text to construct meaning. These are further

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
enhanced through rhetorical strategies such as foregrounding, Intensity, backgrounding,
and which draw attention to key messages and amplify their communicative impact.

Syntactically, the headline " World Pneumonia Day" is a noun phrase. Noun phrases are short and precise. It draws attention to pneumonia as a serious global health issue. Also, foregrounding, as a rhetorical means of highlighting key linguistic elements, is employed to reinforce the clarity of the message. This is achieved through the use of capital letters "WORLD PNEUMONIA DAY". This is to visually disrupt the normal flow of text, grabbing the attention of the audience. This is done to create a sense of urgency and raise awareness about a day dedicated to providing medical attention for pneumonia disease. The supporting texts "Every Breath Counts" is a simple declarative sentence used to emphasize the value of each breath, this connotes urgency in saving every breath by prevention through seeking medical interventions to cure it

The follow-up text "Stop Pneumonia Now" is an imperative sentence suggesting urgency. "Now" intensifies the command and emphasises immediacy. This is done to create awareness of the seriousness of the disease.

In the text above, intensity is achieved through the use of bright colours and other contrasting colours. The colour used for the background of the flyer is white, and other colours are used for the supporting texts on the background, which is to make it clear to understand (it achieves legibility). It makes the message easy to access and understand. Another semiotic device used in the text above, as mentioned earlier, is background. Generally, background elements are elements placed below the foregrounded elements, without distracting viewers from the main message. It is to subtly reinforce the message passed across through the foregrounded elements, while "World Pneumonia Day" names the event, "Every Breath Counts" adds emotional and moral weight. It amplifies the seriousness of pneumonia, a disease that affects breathing, by emphasising that each breath is valuable. It makes the reader reflect on the life-or-

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al JOES 2025 1(1)
death importance of breathing, thus reinforcing why the day matters. In the text, the background elements " It is also to create a context for the foregrounded elements;" World Pneumonia Day' alone might not fully communicate why the day is important."Every breath counts" helps frame the day as one focused on awareness, urgency, and human vulnerability. It guides interpretation; the viewer now knows this isn't just a medical or calendar event; it's about protecting lives.

Visual Mode Analysis

Within the visual mode, images and colours are used to communicate; this is done through the use of semiotic resources like background, intensity, framing, foregrounding, coherence, among others. These resources are used to enhance communication and to reinforce the meaning of the message. In the text above, the dominant semiotic resources used are foregrounding and intensity.

As mentioned above, one of the visual modes used to enhance communication in the text is foregrounding. Generally, foregrounding is a stylistic strategy used to draw attention to a particular element. This can be achieved by using large font sizes for images, incorporating bright or contrasting colours, and placing images at the centre or top of the flyer to capture the viewer's attention. The image of a stethoscope symbolises care, health, and medicine. It is placed at the centre of the poster to foreground the message. In the context of visual analysis, foregrounding is a stylistic strategy used to draw attention to a particular element. The placement of the stethoscope at the centre of the poster is designed to captivate the viewers' attention and draw it to the centre. It is a visual metaphor that connects healthcare with love and urgency, reinforcing the emotional and medical importance of pneumonia awareness. Additionally, the use of white as the background colour and other contrasting colours for linguistic and visual elements helps to foreground the message, thereby enhancing accessibility.

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**

Also, the image of a lung icon with bronchial tubes symbolises the primary organ affected by pneumonia, and the red colour is used for this image to show the danger in the lungs affected by pneumonia. This is done to intensify the message. This is to appeal to the emotion of fear in the minds of the audience to ensure a prompt response to preventing the disease.

Integration of Modes

These two modes (linguistic and visual) are combined to reinforce the message of urgency and to create awareness of the deadly disease. Red colour connotes danger and urgency (Kress 2002), and so, in the text, red colour is used for the image of the lungs to show the danger in the lungs affected by pneumonia. It is also used in the text "Pneumonia" to indicate the danger of the disease and to raise an alarm to ensure a prompt response in preventing and curing the disease.

DIARRHEA DISEASE

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
resources deployed in them, and how the modes interact to pass the intended message to the audience.

Linguistic Mode Analysis

Within the linguistic mode, features such as sentence types, lexical choices and syntactic properties are used in the text to construct meaning. These are further enhanced through rhetorical strategies such as foregrounding, Intensity, backgrounding, and which draw attention to key messages and amplify their communicative impact.

The rhetorical device used in the text above is foregrounding.

Syntactically, the " Foods to Avoid When You Have Diarrhoea" is a non-finite clause. It lacks a finite verb and subject. It functions as a headline. It is instructional, prompt and grabs the attention of the audience. It captures the reader's attention because it addresses an urgent health concern in simple, action-oriented language.

To enhance the immediate recognition and accessibility of the headline, it is stylistically foregrounded. In the text, foregrounding is achieved through capital letters. "FOOD TO AVOID WHEN YOU HAVE DIARRHEA" It is foregrounded to grab the attention and thought of the audience to the message, which is to inform the audience on the preventive measures against pneumonia.

Under the lexical choice, an inclusive pronoun is used in the text above. "You" in "Foods to Avoid when you have diarrhoea" is an inclusive pronoun, it is to engage the reader directly. van Dijk notes that " inclusive pronouns are used to build solidarity and create a sense of collective action". In the text, an inclusive pronoun is used to communicate directly to the reader. It makes the message personal and engaging. The supporting text: " hot pepper, nuts, coffee, alcohol, citrus, fruit, red meat, legumes, sugar substitute, cruciferous, vegetables" are lexical resources used to label the images. They are also foregrounded using capital letters to ensure clarity and easy accessibility.

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al JOES 2025 1(1)

Also, they symbolise care, health and prevention because images are never innocent; they are always coded and culturally situated signs (Barthes, 1977)

The follow-up text: "To explore more, visit [www. Top10 Home Remedy. Com](http://www.Top10HomeRemedy.Com)" is an imperative sentence; it is clear and concise. It gives further guidance on how to get more information in curing the deadly disease.

Visual Mode Analysis

Within the visual mode, images and colours are used to communicate; this is done through the use of semiotic resources like background, intensity, framing, foregrounding, coherence, among others. These resources are used to enhance communication and to reinforce the meaning of the message. In the text above, the dominant semiotic device used is visual metaphor and foregrounding.

The image of a man who is pouring out milk into a toilet is symbolic. The toilet symbolises waste, rejection, or contamination. Pouring milk into the toilet conveys avoidance or prohibition to indicate that the food is harmful for diarrhoea patients. The toilet is a visual metaphor. Forceville (1996:10), supports this claim by stating that "visual metaphors rely on the substitution of one domain for another, with one image standing in for another concept or evaluation.". Also, the positioning of the man's image is to achieve visual framing. Generally, framing is directing the reader's attention through lay out, positioning or visual focus the text above, framing is achieved through the positioning of the image at the center of the flyer to attract the attention and focus of the audience to the message being passed across by his gesture which is intended to suggest foods that should be avoided when suffering from diarrhea.

Also, in the text above, the visual communication is context-based because the milk and red meat that the man is trying to dispose of are not naturally harmful but specifically harmful to diarrhoea patients, as used in this context. To support this, Jewitt

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al JOES 2025 1(1) and Oyama (2001:140) state that "visual communication is context bound. Its meaning depends on shared cultural knowledge and interpretative framework". The intended meaning is to show the danger of consuming these foods when suffering from diarrhoea. Thus, the image uses metaphorical rejection to warn the viewer. It is effective for low literacy viewers or audiences, as it communicates meaning without required reading. The image of a hand offering alcohol and the other hand rejecting it is also symbolic; the hands are not just a part of the body, they represent the entire person's choice or moral stance. The hand offering the alcohol may represent a temptation, peer pressure or unhealthy behaviour. The hand is a metonymic sign. They stand for larger social or behavioural identities.

Gestural Mode Analysis

In the flyer, a hand is shown offering an alcoholic drink, and another hand is stretched out to reject it. These gestures (hand movements) are important and significant in passing the message. The stretched hand shows someone trying to offer alcohol. This gesture represents a social situation, like a friend offering a drink. The rejection hand, stretched out, clearly means "No". It tells the viewer not to accept the alcohol. These gestures suggest that the diarrhoea patient should avoid alcohol. They help explain the message without words, making it easy for anyone to understand, even a non-literate audience.

The man's facial expression and body movement (pouring milk into the toilet) express disapproval or rejection of these foods. His gesture of holding red meat at a distance reinforces the idea of discarding it, not consuming it. This is done to add emotional and behavioural cues to reinforce the "avoidance" message. It is a way of intensifying the message.

Spatial Mode Analysis

The foods are grouped around the central image, creating a clear structure. The circular layout guides the eyes from the centre outward, helping to absorb all the visual and textual elements. The central positioning of the man and the toilet draws immediate focus and importance. This is done to organise the information clearly and prioritise the central message visually.

Integration Modes:

All the modes work synergistically to reinforce the message. The image complements the text: The man pouring milk and holding meat vividly illustrates the instruction “avoid these foods” in a memorable way. The text completes the image: The linguistic labels identify and clarify what each image represents, making the visuals more informative.

Ensure the information is quickly understood by a broad audience, including those with limited literacy skills.

MEASLES DISEASE

MEASLES DISEASE

The above text has a combination of two modes: the linguistic mode and the visual mode. What follows is an analysis of each of these modes, the semiotic resources deployed in them, and how the modes interact to pass the intended message to the audience.

Linguistic Analysis

Within the linguistic mode, features such as sentence types, lexical choices and syntactic properties are used in the text to construct meaning. These are further enhanced through rhetorical strategies such as foregrounding, Intensity, backgrounding, and which draw attention to key messages and amplify their communicative impact.

Syntactically, the headline "Is it Measles?" is an interrogative sentence. It is a rhetorical question used to engage the audience directly. The headline immediately captures attention by raising a question that causes the audience to think critically about symptoms they or their children may be experiencing to enhance the immediate recognition and accessibility of the headline, it is stylistically foregrounded. In the text, foregrounding is achieved through capital letters. It is designed to capture the audience's attention and convey the message.

The supporting text "Measles is serious and it spreads to a lot of people really fast" is a compound declarative sentence. It has two independent clauses: "Measles is serious" and "it spreads to a lot of people really fast". A coordinating conjunction joins it "and". It is used to educate the audience on the severity of measles. The fact that it is contagious is also emphasised so as to create a sense of urgency in curing it.

Under the lexical choice, emotive language is used. In the text, "serious" is an emotive language that appeals to the emotion of fear to prompt them to seek curative measures immediately. The phrase "it spreads to lots of people, real fast" uses repetition and the

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
informal intensifier “real fast” to emphasise how contagious measles is. This choice of words is to amplify the seriousness and create an emotional impact on the viewer.

The supporting texts "rash of red spots on face and body, fever, running nose, cough, red sore, watery eyes", linguistically educate the audience on the symptoms of the disease.

Visual Mode Analysis

Images accompany the linguistic elements to illustrate the symptoms. This aims to achieve clarity and reach the low-literacy audience. The use of deep red as the background colour creates urgency and danger, typical of warning or alert messages. This is to achieve visual intensity. Also, the red rashes, red eyes, and tears are visually exaggerated to highlight severity. Facial expression of the main child: Eyes wide open, mouth slightly agape, brows raised, these express discomfort and alertness to pain or sickness. The central image of the sick child with red spots is foregrounded. It is larger and centrally placed to grab attention. This central placement signals that the rash is the most identifiable and severe symptom, guiding the viewer's focus.

Gestural Mode Analysis

The child scratching his body visually depicts itching caused by measles rashes. Other children's gestures: Covering mouth (cough), Using tissue (runny nose), Crying with eyes closed tight (red, sore, watery eyes). These gestures visually enact the symptoms and help communicate the effects of measles nonverbally, making the message accessible even without reading the text.

Integration Modes

All these modes are not used in isolation but work interdependently to enhance meaning. The images illustrate the textual elements; the gestures further illustrate the symptoms to create emotional impact. Through this multimodal integration, the flyer successfully raises awareness and educates the public about the symptoms and dangers of measles in a visually compelling and linguistically accessible way.

HIV DISEASE

TEXT 5

Linguistic Mode Analysis

Within the linguistic mode, features such as sentence types, lexical choices and syntactic properties are used in the text to construct meaning. These are further enhanced through rhetorical strategies such as foregrounding, Intensity, backgrounding, and which draw attention to key messages and amplify their communicative impact. The rhetorical device used in the text above is foregrounding.

In the text above, the headline "Warning signs of HIV " is a noun phrase. It is short and clear. This is to create awareness of the symptoms of HIV. To enhance the immediate recognition and accessibility of the headline, it is stylistically foregrounded. In the text, foregrounding is achieved through capitalisation. This is to draw the attention of the audience to it. Under the lexical choice, an emotive verb is used. "Warning" in warning signs of HIV is an emotive verb that appeals to the emotion of fear and connotes danger. It is used to raise an alarm about the deadly disease and prompt a quick response in seeking medical intervention if symptoms are observed.

Visual Analysis

The upper image shows a person pointing to a swollen lymph node on the neck, a common early symptom of HIV. This gesture draws attention to physical changes on the body that should not be ignored. The lower image depicts a mouth ulcer (oral thrush or sore), another visible sign associated with HIV infection. The redness and the ulcerated area reinforce the seriousness of the symptom. Colour plays a central role in meaning-making within multimodal texts. It functions like grammar and structures information. The background is white, which ensures high contrast and visual clarity. The words "WARNING SIGNS OF HIV" are in bold capital letters, using red and blue. Red (used for "WARNING" and "HIV") connotes danger, urgency, and health risk,

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
drawing immediate attention. Blue (used for “SIGNS OF”) adds a calming, informative tone, balancing the emotional intensity.

Spatial Mode Analysis

The division into left (images) and right (text) encourages a left-to-right reading flow. First, seeing the problem (symptoms), then understanding what it means (warning about HIV).

Integration Of Modes

The flyer integrates visual mode, linguistic mode and spatial mode effectively to reinforce its message: The linguistic text ("WARNING SIGNS OF HIV") provides a summary frame for the images. Without this text, the images may not be clearly understood as HIV-related. Similarly, the images give visual proof and context to the text, making the warning relatable.

Discussion of Findings

This section presents the key findings that emerged from the multimodal analysis of the twenty (20) selected flyers on children-related diseases in Nigeria.

Predominant Use of Linguistic Mode: Most of the flyers rely heavily on direct and imperative sentence structures such as “Get your child vaccinated” and “Malaria kills.” These were often reinforced with emotionally charged lexical choices (e.g., “serious,” “life-threatening,” “protect,” “save lives”), which serve to persuade and alert the audience to the urgency of the health issue.

Strategic Use of Visual Mode: The flyers made effective use of images, colours, and layout to reinforce their messages. For instance, red was commonly used to signify danger or urgency. At the same time, green and blue often symbolised health and safety.

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al JOES 2025 1(1)

Images of sick or healthy children were used to evoke emotion, represent disease symptoms, or model the desired health behaviour.

Gestural Communication in Images: Gestures such as facial expressions (sadness, discomfort, or happiness), hand positioning (e.g., stretched arms or protective holding), and body posture (e.g., slouched or upright) were found to represent illness, vulnerability, or care visually. These gestures humanised the message and created emotional appeal.

Spatial Arrangement for Clarity and Impact: Texts were generally placed on one side of the flyer, with images occupying the other half or positioned centrally. This left-to-right or top-to-bottom reading path followed natural cognitive processing and made the flyers easier to navigate. Headings were often bold and positioned at the top, serving as immediate attention-grabbers.

Integration of Modes Enhancing Meaning: Across most flyers, there was a strong synergy between modes. The combination of commanding texts with emotionally expressive images and purposeful layouts helped to deepen understanding and influence perception. The integration of modes was not accidental but intentional, aimed at persuading, informing, and provoking behavioural change.

Use of Semiotic Resources: Foregrounding (highlighting key messages in bold or red), intensity (exaggerated emotional tone), and framing (visual borders around images or texts) were shared across the flyers. These resources enhanced focus and directed the viewer's attention to critical parts of the message.

The findings show that multimodal elements work together to make children-related disease awareness more effective in Nigeria. The use of language, images, gestures, and spatial arrangements ensures the message is not only seen but also felt and understood by the target audience.

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al JOES 2025 1(1)

This study investigated how multimodal resources are deployed in health communication through the analysis of 20 selected flyers on five major children-related diseases in Nigeria: malaria, pneumonia, HIV/AIDS, diarrhoea, and measles. Using a multimodal discourse analysis framework, the research examined how different semiotic modes linguistic, visual, spatial, and gestural—interact to create and reinforce meaning, convey urgency, and influence behavioural change.

The analysis revealed that all twenty (20) flyers employed a variety of communicative modes—linguistic, visual, gestural, and spatial—each contributing uniquely to meaning-making. The linguistic mode served as the primary carrier of information, often using short, direct, and imperative sentences to instruct or persuade the audience.

The visual mode, expressed through the use of images, colours, and graphic layout, helped reinforce the seriousness and preventability of diseases such as malaria, HIV, measles, pneumonia, and diarrhoea. The gestural mode, through facial expressions and body postures in images, conveyed emotion and made the messages more relatable and human-centred. The spatial mode—including how images, headings, and text blocks were arranged—played a significant role in directing the attention and organising information for easy ,straightforward interpretation.

Furthermore, the study showed that the integration of these modes enhanced the communicative power of the flyers. Rather than functioning in isolation, the modes were deliberately combined to reinforce, expand, and enrich the health messages being conveyed. For example, textual descriptions of symptoms were often accompanied by real-life images depicting affected children, allowing for visual reinforcement of the message. Colour choices aligned with the emotional tone of the contentred for danger, blue for trust, green for safety while spatial arrangements helped ensure that the most important information stood out. This multimodal synergy created a dynamic communicative environment that allowed viewers to process information through

Multimodal Discourse... Peace Oluwapelumi Popoola et al **JOES 2025 1(1)**
multiple semiotic cues, thereby improving understanding, emotional engagement, and recall.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that multimodal discourse strategies are highly effective in shaping public health communication, especially when dealing with issues as sensitive and urgent as children-related diseases. The dynamic interaction between linguistic, visual, gestural, and spatial modes, supported by semiotic resources, enables the production of flyers that do not merely inform but also persuade, warn, and evoke empathy. This underscores the importance of multimodality in creating impactful health messages that resonate with diverse audiences in a culturally and socially complex context like Nigeria.

- Kreps, G. L. (1988). Relational communication in health care. *Southern Communication Journal*, 53(4), 344–358. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10417948809372663>
- National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] & ICF International. (2014).
Odebunmi, A. (2006). Locutions in medical discourse in Southwestern Nigeria. *Pragmatics*, 16(1), 25–41.
- Olajimbiti, E. O. (2025). Deontic Modality and Evaluation of Obligations in Children-related X (Twitter) Interactions. *Corpus Pragmatics*, 1-22.
- Oyebode, O., & Unuabonah, F. O. (2018). Reconsidering the role of language in medicine. *Philosophy, Ethics, and Humanities in Medicine*, 13, Article 5.
- Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2013). Abuja, Nigeria, and Rockville, Maryland, USA: NPC and ICF International. <https://dhsprogram.com/publications/publication-fr293-dhs-final-reports.cfm>
- UNICEF Nigeria. (2021). Health and nutrition. United Nations Children's Fund. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/health-and-nutrition>
- World Health Organisation. (2020). Levels and trends in child mortality: Report 2020. United Nations Inter-agency Group for Child Mortality Estimation (UN IGME). <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240013432>
- World Health Organisation. (2013). Health promotion: Glossary of terms 2013. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241505028>
- O'Halloran, K. L. (2004). *Multimodal discourse analysis: Systemic functional perspectives*. London: Continuum.